

Modeling of Miniaturized Microstrip Patch Antenna having Concentric Polygon Shaped with Eight Segments Slots based on DGS for Multiband Wireless Applications using Parametric Analysis

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Abstract

A highly miniaturized microstrip patch antenna using defected ground structure (DGS) loading Concentric Polygon shaped with eight segments slots (CPSESS) is presented in this paper. Initially a conventional antenna of active radiator area of 841mm^2 and volume of about 6136mm^3 is designed at 2.4GHz, for FR4 substrate, it is resonating for dual band operation of bandwidth of 43.5MHz and 160.2MHz. This antenna is miniaturized by employing novel DGS comprising of CPSESS. It result new model of highly compact size, i.e. active radiator with volume miniaturized 441mm^2 , 3427mm^3 . Thus, providing reducing in size 52.43% & 55.85% as compared to conventional antenna. Further the proposed model exhibit multiband band frequency by varying size of slots of CPSESS on DGS by parametric analysis. The antenna also shows acceptable gain of all frequency band around 1.06 dB. The obtained resonance, bandwidth, gain and radiation performance proposed model makes it suitable multiple wireless applications such as for WLAN, Radar and X-band.

Keywords:- DGS, patch antenna, modelling multiband, FR4 substrate, miniaturization, Parametric variables.

1. Introduction

Because of advancements in wireless technology, antenna engineers face a significant challenge in designing compact antennas that can be used for a variety of compact portable wireless devices. As device sizes shrink, the dedicated area for antenna slots in the device shrinks as well.

Creating a small antenna with acceptable performance is a difficult task. This is due to the fact that as the antenna's size decreases, the wavelength decreases, affecting the antenna's impedance behaviour [1-3]. As a result, making these parameters acceptable at smaller sizes becomes difficult. Nonetheless, various design techniques for miniaturising antenna size have been presented in the literature, such as metamaterials [4-7], shorting pins [8], slots [9-12], defected ground structure (DGS) [13-17], and so on. In addition to miniaturisation, multiband operation from a single antenna is highly desirable these days. This reduces the need for multiple antenna elements to be deployed for each desired operating band.

Recently, the DGS method for miniaturising antennas and obtaining multiband behaviour has piqued the interest of researchers. The main advantage of this method is that by utilising this structure, the surface current flow of the antenna changes, resulting in a deviation of inductance and capacitance, thus miniaturising the size of the antenna. Aside from that, the DGS method has the advantage of being simple to integrate antennas with monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMIC). As a result, various antennas based on this configuration are reported in the literature [13-16]. Two DGS structures were used in a [12] to miniaturise the antenna and achieve triple band operation. The slotted DGS structure is used in [13] to miniaturise the UWB antenna. In [14], fractal geometry and an open ended slot are used to reduce the overall size of the antenna. Similarly, in [15], a concentric ring-based structure is used to reduce the volume of a circular-shaped antenna.

This study proposes a novel DGS structure by miniaturising a conventionally designed microstrip antenna using CPSESS. Overall miniaturisation achieved is approximately 52.71 percent in radiator area and approximately 55.85 percent in volume. With the help of, the proposed model shrinks in size and its overall behaviour is explained. Parametric studies are also carried out in order to determine the optimal antenna dimension. The designed antenna operates in multiple bands, making it suitable for WLAN, radar, and X-band applications.

2. Design Configuration and Result Analysis

The purpose of this paper is to design a highly miniaturized antenna by utilizing the concept of defected ground structure (DGS) by loading Concentric Polygon shaped with eight segments slots (CPSESS). Initially a conventional "Ant. 1" is taken into consideration for miniaturization. This antenna has a square patch structure and is fed by microstrip line feed as depicted in Figure 1. The antenna has an overall substrate size of $65 \times 59 = 6136 \text{ mm}^2$ and radiator area of $29 \times 29 = 841 \text{ mm}^2$. The reflection co-efficient (S_{11}) (equ.1) of this antenna is shown in Figure 2. Wherein it can be visually perceived that, it gives resonance at 2.4, 7.12 GHz frequency with BW of 43.5MHz & 160.2MHz. As the size of this antenna is large, so DGS methodology is incorporated to further reduce the size of this "Ant. 1".

FIG. 1:Microstrip patch antenna miniaturization process using DGS

In the “Ant. 2” configuration of Figure 1, it is seen that a DGS is etched out. The inclusion of this structure miniaturizes the conventional antenna to a substrate size of $51 \times 42 = 2142 \text{ mm}^2$ and the radiator size $21 \times 21 = 441 \text{ mm}^2$. Hence, reduction in size by 55.85% and 52.43%. The S_{11} response of this is depicted in Figure 2. As the creation of DGS affects the overall wavelength of the antenna, the S_{11} response gets shifted upwards, resonating at three bands of frequency. Further investigation on Ant.2, the ground plane reduced by 8mm, this results in Ant.3, the response shifted slightly towards the lower side as compared to Ant.2, with enhancing the BW, RL resonating at 3.18GHz, 6.17GHz, 6.26GHz with minimum return loss are -31.15db, -33.19db, -33.19dBGHz, bandwidth of BW=105MHz, BW=173MHz, BW=175MHz, respectively, as shown in Fig.2.

FIG.2: Miniaturization process S_{11} response of Ant.1, Ant.2, Ant.3, Ant.4

Ant.3. Structure provides size in reeducation by 55.8% as compared to conventional square patch antenna.

$$S_{11} \text{ (dB)} = 20 \log (P_{\text{ref}} / P_{\text{in}}) \quad \dots\dots\text{eq-(1)}$$

$$\text{Bandwidth} = \text{BW}(\%) = ((f_H - f_L) / f_r) * 100 \quad \dots\dots\text{eq-(2)}$$

for further modification on DGS by loading Concentric Polygon shaped with eight segments slots on DGS by varying width of slots at p=1mm by optimization by using parametric analysis get desire multiband frequency operations as shown in Fig.3. and proposed antenna 4 As shown in Fig.4. Thus the DGS structure helps in achieving fundamental frequency with multiple band of frequency and the overall compactness , this leads multiband frequencies of operation at $f_1=2.54\text{GHz}$, $f_2=5.8\text{GHz}$, $f_3=6.96\text{GHz}$, $f_4=8.4\text{GHz}$, $f_5=10.2\text{GHz}$, $f_6=11.17\text{GHz}$, with minimum return loss -15.90db, -14db, -14.9db, -28.10db, -12.62db, -19.33db and respective band width BW=43MHz, BW=318MHz, BW=412MHz, BW=419MHz, BW=734MHz, BW=702MHz. the response of Ant.4 shown in Fig.3. In comparison to the conventional antenna the proposed antenna 4 acquires the compactness of about 55.719% and 52.43% in radiator area as given in Table 1

FIG. 3: proposed l Antenna.4 S11 response

Table 1: Comparison of size reduction Ant.1, Ant.2., Ant.3, & Ant.4-Pro
[613]

Parameters	Size (mm ³)	Area of radiator	Volume of the antenna	Miniaturization achieved (%)
Ant. 1	65.56x59.56x1.6	29x29=841	6136	-
Ant. 2	51x42x1.6	21x21=441	3427	55.85 and 52.43
Ant.3	Modification Ant.2 by reducing Ground plane by 8mm, it result multiband and enhance in BW,RL but designed frequency 2.4GHz not achieved.			--
Ant.4 Prop. Antenna	Further investigating Ant.3 by lodging CPSESS on ground plane by varying slot width p=1mm , it result in multiband frequency at $f_1 = 2.54$, $f_2 = 5.8$, $f_3 = 6.9$, $f_4 = 8.4$, $f_5 = 10.25$ & $f_6 = 11.1$ GHz			

Table 2: Designed parameter of CSMSA and miniaturized proposed model Dimension antenna

Antenna parameters	Dimensions of CSMSA in mm	Dimension miniaturized proposed model Dimension in mm	% of miniaturized in Size
Substrate	65.56x59.56	51x42	55.719%
patch	29x29	21x21	52.43%
Length(L_f) & width(W_f) of QT	15.0288 & 3.1642	11.762 & --	22.6 %
Length(L_f) & width(W_f) of feed	15.1562 & 0.7185	11.76 & --	23.27%
CPSESS	---	Radius of 12,10,8,4 , slots width very between P= 0 to 1mm	P=1mm

Antenna	Resonant frequency in GHz	Return Loss in dB	Band Width MHz	Band Width %
CSMSA	2.40 & 7.12	-12.9 & -21.4	43.5 & 160.2	1.812 & 2.25
Proposed Model	$f_1 = 2.54$	-15.90	43	2.727
	$f_2 = 5.8$	-14.5	318	6.023
	$f_3 = 6.96$	-14.9	412	5.841
	$f_4 = 8.4$	-28.10	419	5.841
	$f_5 = 10.2$	-12.62	734	0.773

	$f_6 = 11.17$	-19.33	702	1.221
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Table – 3: The simulated results are summarized of proposed Antenna

FIG. 4: Proposed Antenna.4 detailed configuration of using CPSESS on DGS

The detailed dimensional configuration of the said design is depicted in Figure 4. The final design consists an overall size of $51 \times 42 \text{mm}^2$ and is built on FR4 material ($h=1.6 \text{mm}$, $\delta = 0.02$ and $\epsilon_r = 4.4$). The front patch of the antenna consists square radiator having the 21×21 area, and is fed by microstrip line using quarter wave transform. In the ground by loading CPSESS slots width of 1mm apart optimization by using parametric analysis get desire multiband frequency Thus the DGS structure helps in achieving the overall compactness it leads multiband frequency of operation at 2.5477, 5.8643, 6.9698, 8.407, 10.2588 & 11.1 GHz in Shown in Fig.3.

3. Details Explanation Parametric Analysis

The parametric analysis is very important part of the antenna design as it helps in optimizing the final dimension of the antenna based on the impedance behavior. Thus, to finalize the dimension of the antenna four important parametric investigations are carried out. There are variation changes in the width of the feedline (L_f), width of the QW(L_f), & size patch, ground plane, substrate reduced as compare to Fig 1 &3. Fig.3 by varying slot of Concentric Polygon shaped with eight segments slot based on DGS by assigning variable $p=0$ to 1 step size 0.1, by parametric analysis got the desire result at $p=1 \text{mm}$ for multiband wireless applications. Respectively as depicted in Figure.4.

From Figure 4, it can be seen that when the slot of CPSESS is varied from the fixed dimension ($P_5=0\text{mm}$ and 0.5mm) there is a drastic change in the impedance behavior of the antenna. From Figure 4, when $P_3=1\text{mm}$ get the desired response for multiband operations.

FIG. 4: Parametric investigation of the antenna for: varying slot of CPSESS based on DGS ($P_1=0\text{mm}$, $P_2=0.5\text{mm}$, $P_3=1\text{mm}$ slots with varied to obtained multiband.

The final antenna is simulated in Ansys HFSS using Finite Element Method (FEM). The S_{11} plot of the antenna is given in Figure 3. The antenna exhibits multiband resonance, the acceptable bandwidth wireless communications. The maximum value of S_{11} achieved is around -15.8922 , -13.9396 , -14.4908 , -28.1099 , -12.6212 , & -19.3327 in dB, thus ensuring good impedance matching at all the Bands.

The 3D gain patter plot of the antenna is illustrated in the Figure 6. At 2.5477 , 5.8643 , 6.9698 , 8.407 , 10.2588 & 11.1 GHz, are 1.61dB , 5.28dB , 3.95dB , 4.26dB , 7.036dB & 1.002dB its observed. One can visualize here that, gain is not uniform which is primarily due to the miniaturization in the antenna, which changes the overall operating wavelength of the antenna.

Fig.6: 3D gain pattern: 2.54GHz(a) , 5.86 GHz(b), 6.9 GHz(c), 8.4 GHz(d), 10.25 GHz(e) & 11.1 GHz(f) .

At all the resonance frequency, antenna ensures stable radiation patterns with dipole like characteristics 2.5, 5.8, 6.9, 8.4, 10.2 & 11.1 GHz,. However, at 5.8643GHz, 10.2588 GHz the pattern appears to be little bit distorted which is mainly to due to the miniaturization of the antenna and higher order resonant mode exited simultaneously.

Fig.7: The radiation pattern of the antenna is given in Fig.7: radiation pattern: 2.54GHz(a) , 5.86 GHz(b), 6.9 GHz(c), 8.4 GHz(d), 10.25 GHz(e) & 11.1 GHz(f) .

4. Conclusion

A study on miniaturization process of microstrip patch antenna using DGS is carried out in this paper. The employed miniaturization structure finally resulted in a compact active radiator area of only $21 \times 21 = 441 \text{ mm}^2$, thereby resulting in 52.43 % miniaturization as compared to conventional antenna. And by using CPSESS on ground plane based on DGS results in multiband frequency by varying width of the CPSESS, it result multiband $f_1= 2.54\text{GHz}, -15.90\text{db}, \text{BW}=43\text{MHz}$; $f_2=5.8\text{GHz}, -14\text{db}, \text{BW}=318\text{MHz}$; $f_3=6.96\text{GHz}, -14.9\text{db}, \text{BW}=412\text{MHz}$; $f_4=8.4\text{GHz}, -28.10\text{db}, \text{BW}=419\text{MHz}$; $f_5=10.2\text{GHz}, -12.62\text{db}, \text{BW}=734\text{MHz}$; $f_6=11.17\text{GHz}, -19.33\text{db}, \text{BW}=702\text{MHz}$. The designed antenna also depicts multiband frequency of operations and is suitable to be used for wireless application such as WLAN, Radar and X-band range. The antenna also depicts acceptable gain and radiation pattern at the obtained resonance. The antenna provides advantage of very compact size, planar configuration, ease of design and stable radiation performance characteristics, thereby making it very efficient to be employed for mentioned applications.

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